

A HYPOTHESIS OF REGULARITY IN THE DISTRIBUTION OF COMPOSITE AND PRIME NUMBERS

MARCO BRIZIO

ABSTRACT. In this work, we propose a hypothesis according to which composite and prime numbers emerge as a manifestation of an underlying continuous principle when discretization elements are introduced into it. This hypothesis is supported by a specific continuous, closed, and predictably distributed function that characterizes the behavior of such numbers within a continuous domain.

The construction of this function is based on a diagram (referred to as the Divisibility Diagram) that is algorithmically generated. Initially, an equation is formulated to represent this diagram within a mixed domain of real and integer numbers. Subsequently, a function operating in a continuous domain is obtained. By analyzing its properties of continuity, closure, and predictable distribution, the aforementioned hypothesis is formulated.

1. INTRODUCTION

Prime numbers represent a fascinating and complex challenge for number theory, due to their seemingly irregular distribution and their fundamental importance in many areas of mathematics. However, despite significant theoretical progress, the true essence of prime numbers remains shrouded in mystery. The idea behind this work emerged unexpectedly from a simple graphical representation (inspired by the Sieve of Eratosthenes). Imagining a Cartesian grid, each column was populated with dots placed at increasing intervals: in the first column, every intersection; in the second, every two intersections; in the third, every three intersections, and so on (see Figure 1).

Among the various characteristics of the diagram thus constructed, the possibility of visually distinguishing between prime and composite numbers emerged. Due to its very construction, dots are placed on each row corresponding to the divisors of the respective value y . On row 6, for example, we find the dots in columns 1, 2, 3, and 6. All the rows corresponding to prime numbers are therefore easily identifiable, as they only contain two dots: one in column 1 and the other at the intersection with the $x = y$ line.

A HYPOTHESIS OF REGULARITY IN THE DISTRIBUTION OF
COMPOSITE AND PRIME NUMBERS

FIGURE 1. The Divisibility Diagram

2. THE DIVISIBILITY DIAGRAM FORMULA

Is it possible to define a formula to draw the Divisibility Diagram instead of using an algorithm? To do this, we need to use an element of cyclicity, such as the equation:

$$\cos(2\pi y) = 1$$

Which is satisfied for every integer value of y . If we want the interval between the solutions to assume a specific value, we need to introduce the variable x into the previous equation:

$$\cos\left(\frac{2\pi y}{x}\right) = 1 \quad (\text{B})$$

As a result, we obtain the equation that represents the locus of points of the Divisibility Diagram within the domain $x \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ $y \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. From now on, we will refer to it as the base equation or Equation B. The variable x has been restricted to

positive integers to prevent the diagram's symmetry with respect to the y -axis and to ensure that there are no solutions of B in where y is not an integer. The variable y has been restricted to $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ to prevent the diagram's symmetry with respect to the x -axis.

It would now be interesting to modify Equation B in order to extend its domain of x to real numbers. Reality itself appears (at least at the macroscopic level) continuous and not discretized, and in this way, we could explore a scenario in which integers emerge from a real domain.

For this purpose, let us consider the equation:

$$\cos(2\pi x) = 1 \quad (\text{RZ})$$

That is satisfied for every value of x belonging to the set of integers. From now on, we will refer to it as Equation RZ (since it will be used in conjunction with the base equation to involve real variables and yield integer solutions).

If we sum the left-hand sides of B and RZ and set them equal to 2, we obtain the BRZ equation:

$$\cos\left(\frac{2\pi y}{x}\right) + \cos(2\pi x) = 2 \quad (\text{BRZ})$$

That is, the locus of points of the Divisibility Diagram in the domain $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $y \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. The solutions of BRZ have integer values because, for it to be satisfied, both addends on its left-hand side must be equal to 1: in the second addend, this occurs only when x is an integer, and similarly, in the first addend, when the result of the division $\frac{y}{x}$ is an integer, which can only happen when y is also an integer. The two addends of BRZ can also be seen as families of lines, so it can be said that the points of the Divisibility Diagram are, as shown in Figure 2, identified by the intersection of the two families:

$$\mathcal{B} = \{y = mx \mid m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \text{ e } \mathcal{RZ} = \{x = n \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$$

As a brief digression, let us consider the equation:

$$N_{\text{BRZ}}(y) = 2 \quad (1)$$

Where N denotes the number of solutions of the BRZ equation for a fixed value of y . Recalling that in the Divisibility Diagram, all rows containing exactly two points correspond to prime numbers, we can state that in the domain $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $y \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, Equation 1 is satisfied only when y is prime.

A HYPOTHESIS OF REGULARITY IN THE DISTRIBUTION OF
COMPOSITE AND PRIME NUMBERS

FIGURE 2. The Divisibility Diagram as the intersection of families of lines \mathcal{B} e \mathcal{RZ}

FIGURE 3. Solutions of the BRZ equation in the domain $1 < x < y, \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R}_{>1}$

3. BEHAVIOR OF THE BRZ FUNCTION

We now reduce the domain of the BRZ equation to $1 < x < y$, $x, y \in \mathbb{R}_{>1}$. In this way, we eliminate all the solutions previously present on the axes $x = 1$ and $y = x$ (see Figure 3). We have effectively excluded the solutions in which y was divisible only by 1 and itself, that is, those corresponding to a prime number. We can therefore say that the BRZ equation in the domain $1 < x < y$, $x, y \in \mathbb{R}_{>1}$ characterizes composite numbers, as it is satisfied only when y is composite.

3.1. A Graphical Approach. Mathematical functions are not just symbolic expressions; sometimes their complexity and beauty emerge only when observed graphically. Therefore, each function presented in this section is accompanied by its graphical representation to visually appreciate the described properties.

Let us begin with Equation B and transform its left-hand side in a function in (x, y) :

$$B(x, y) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi y}{x}\right)$$

It is continuous, closed, and has a predictable distribution (i.e., it follows a deterministic model, free from chaotic elements) in the domain $1 < x < y$, $x, y \in \mathbb{R}_{>1}$. Its values oscillate between -1 and +1, as shown in Figure 4.

We repeat the same process with the RZ equation, obtaining the function:

$$RZ(x) = \cos(2\pi x)$$

It is also continuous, closed, and has a predictable distribution in the domain of real numbers. Its values oscillate between -1 and +1 (see Figure 5).

Proceeding as above for the BRZ equation, we obtain:

$$BRZ(x, y) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi y}{x}\right) + \cos(2\pi x)$$

It is continuous, closed, and has a predictable distribution (albeit decidedly more complex) in the domain $1 < x < y$, $x, y \in \mathbb{R}_{>1}$. Its values oscillate between -2 and +2, as shown in Figure 6, where values near 0 have been highlighted to emphasize the trend. The blue points are those where the function takes the value 2, and, as can be seen, none of them lie on the red horizontal lines representing the prime numbers.

FIGURE 4. Graph of the function $B(x, y)$ in the domain $1 < x < y$, $x, y \in \mathbb{R}_{>1}$

FIGURE 5. Graph of the function $RZ(x, y)$

FIGURE 6. Graph of the function $BRZ(x, y)$ in the domain
 $1 < x < y, \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R}_{>1}$

4. HYPOTHESIS AND CONCLUSION

We have observed how the distribution of composite numbers is characterized by the function $BRZ(x, y)$ as all the points where its value is 2 have a composite number as their ordinate. We have also noted that this function is continuous, closed, and has a predictable distribution (although intricate due to the interference between the B and RZ functions). It therefore seems reasonable to formulate the hypothesis that the distribution of composite numbers, though complex, is only seemingly irregular. By extension, since prime numbers are complementary to composite numbers for integers greater than 1, we could redefine the hypothesis as follows:

Hypothesis. The distribution of composite and prime numbers, although complex, is only seemingly irregular.

It seems, therefore, that composite and prime numbers are the manifestation of an underlying continuous principle when elements of discretization are introduced. The use of the BRZ function (although it implicitly contains a primality test) has allowed us to view them no longer as the result of an algorithm, but to frame them within a broader context as characterizations of a function with a regular trend. This perspective shifts our perception of their irregularity, making us lose, or at least perceive differently, that aspect of irregularity that previously appeared intrinsic to their distribution. From this new point of view, the distribution of prime and composite numbers would no longer be something chaotic or irregular to analyze ex post, but the inevitable result of a continuous and structured interference process.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank Gennady Eremin for the time he kindly dedicated to me.

REFERENCES

- [1] Atle Selberg (1946)
The distribution of prime numbers. *Mathematica Scandinavica*.
- [2] Bruce C. Berndt (1994)
Ramanujan's Notebooks, Part IV. Springer-Verlag.
- [3] Eratosthenes (200 BCE)
The Sieve of Eratosthenes. *Ancient Mathematics*, 1, 25-30.
- [4] Gennady Eremin (2025)
Infinite matrix of odd natural numbers. A bit about Sophie Germain prime numbers.
arXiv: 2501.17090
- [5] Godfrey H. Hardy and Edward M. Wright (2008)
An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers (6th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- [6] Harold Davenport (1999)
Multiplicative Number Theory (3rd ed.). Springer-Verlag.
- [7] Tom M. Apostol (1976)
Introduction to Analytic Number Theory. Springer-Verlag.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15162684
Email address: contact@mabrix.com